

Delay-Sensitive Task Offloading for Emergency Ambulance in Edge-MEC-Cloud Continuum using Deep Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—In pre-hospital emergency medicine, rapid decisions are critical. AI, 5G, and IoMT can enhance automation, but limited ambulance edge resources, network variability, and changing patient needs in real-time demand intelligent AI task offloading. In such scenarios, dynamic task offloading can optimize real-time computation by considering time sensitivity and resource availability across ambulance edge devices, MEC servers, and cloud servers. This paper presents a patient acuity-aware real-time offloading framework using Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) across the edge-MEC-cloud continuum. The offloading problem is modeled as a Markov Decision Process considering patient acuity, deadlines, computation needs, battery, network, and MEC service availability. Actions select offloading locations to minimize delays and maximize task success. Validation with synthetic dataset shows the PPO model outperforms traditional algorithms in delay sensitivity and task completion under resource constraints.

Index Terms—pre-hospital emergency medicine, edge-MEC-cloud compute continuum, deep reinforcement learning, proximal policy optimization, task offloading, Markov decision process

I. INTRODUCTION

Prehospital emergency medicine (PHEM) requires ambulance personnel to rapidly perform triage, treat and stabilize patients, while sharing crucial patient information with the receiving hospital's emergency department (ED). The European Telecommunications Standards Institute recommends real-time patient data sharing across emergency medicine stakeholders and Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) device integration for continuous patient monitoring [1]. Such rapid decision support systems and automated diagnosis capabilities are essential in time-critical scenarios where treatment delays can significantly worsen patient outcomes.

However, real-time processing of heterogeneous patient data faces significant computational constraints due to limited processing power and battery resources of ambulance edge devices [2], [3]. Computationally-intensive AI tasks such as, including prehospital stroke diagnosis from mobile stroke units, trauma diagnosis from ultrasound videos, ECG analysis for STEMI identification, and EEG analysis for neurological monitoring [4]–[6], often exceed ambulance edge device capabilities. Additionally, HD video streaming for teleconsultation

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requires substantial processing power for real-time compression and transmission, competing for limited network and energy resources [7]–[9]. These limitations necessitate task offloading to mobile edge computing (MEC) servers or cloud servers (CS).

Effective offloading faces additional challenges including network variations in remote locations, dynamic resource availability at MEC nodes, and unpredictable connectivity conditions [10]. Prior collaborative edge-cloud offloading approaches primarily addressed stable scenarios without accounting for network congestion, battery depletion, and demand spikes common in PHEM environments [11]–[13]. Traditional optimization methods [14], [15] require extensive computational time and cannot adapt to rapidly changing conditions, while Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) offers dynamic adaptability [13].

This paper proposes a PHEM-aware DRL framework using Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) for dynamic AI task offloading across ambulance edge device, MEC servers, and CS. Our approach optimizes offloading decisions based on patient triage levels, computational resources, battery constraints, and network conditions. We validate the framework through synthetic PHEM simulations, comparing PPO performance against traditional methods including Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), and Simulated Annealing (SA).

Key contributions:

- A deadline-aware dynamic task offloading framework for PHEM that considers patient acuity levels, resource constraints, and network conditions for optimal allocation across three-tier computing infrastructure.
- Formulation of the task offloading problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) enabling sequential, uncertainty-aware decision making.
- Development and evaluation of a PPO-based algorithm that outperforms traditional optimization methods in handling computationally intensive AI task offloading under dynamic PHEM conditions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Our proposed architecture comprises a three-tier task offloading framework hierarchy: (1) ambulance edge devices, (2) MEC servers, and (3) cloud server, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Tier-1: Ambulance Edge Device Layer

Fig. 1. PHEM-aware three-tier task offloading architecture spanning ambulance edge devices (Tier-1) with IoMT sensors and local AI processing, MEC servers (Tier-2) providing ultra-low latency services, and cloud server (Tier-3) offering centralized storage and heavy AI model processing. Bidirectional communication enables dynamic task allocation based on patient acuity, network conditions, and resource constraints.

The ambulance edge device layer comprises IoMT devices, medical sensors, and edge computing capabilities to generate heterogeneous patient data including vital signs, video streams, ECG/EEG waveforms, ultrasound imaging, and GPS coordinates. Local edge devices perform immediate diagnostic processing using dedicated AI models while maintaining connectivity with upper tiers through roadside units (RSUs) and base station infrastructure.

Ambulance edge devices transmit both raw data and contextual metadata to enable intelligent offloading decisions. Key metadata includes patient acuity levels based on the Netherlands Triage Standard (NTS)¹ ranging from U0 (life-threatening) to U5 (least urgent) along with task deadlines, battery levels, CPU utilization, and network metrics. The NTS urgency levels directly influence task prioritization, with critical patients (U0-U1) receiving priority processing while less urgent cases (U4-U5) allow flexible resource optimization.

Tier-2: Mobile Edge Computing Layer

MEC servers offer intermediate computational resources bridging the gap between resource-constrained ambulance edge devices and distant CS. Although MEC servers are more limited computationally than CS, their proximity enables optimal latency-performance tradeoffs. Connected via fiber-optic links through RSUs and base stations, these servers offer ultra-low latency processing services essential for time-critical PHEM scenarios. MEC servers host AI inference services for

real-time diagnostics and Software Defined Networking (SDN) controllers for dynamic task allocation decisions.

The MEC layer enables intelligent task handoffs between neighboring nodes as ambulances traverse coverage areas and can redirect compute-intensive tasks to CS during peak demand or resource constraints.

Tier-3: Cloud Server Layer

CSs provide extensive computational resources for complex AI tasks including automatic speech recognition, large language model-based report generation, and sophisticated diagnostic algorithms. The CS offers centralized data storage for patient Electronic Health Records (EHRs), heavy AI model processing capabilities, and continuous model retraining services.

CS handle computationally demanding but less time-sensitive tasks such as retrospective analysis, EHR integration, and large-scale data processing. Additionally, CS infrastructure serves as backup processing capability when lower-tier resources are unavailable or overwhelmed, ensuring system resilience across the three-tier compute continuum hierarchy.

A. System Parameters and Task

Let ambulance edge device A , MEC servers M_i ($i = 1, \dots, N$), and CS C form the computing device set $\mathcal{D} = \{A, M_1, \dots, M_N, C\}$ with the respective computational capacities $\{f_A, f_{M_1}, \dots, f_{M_N}, f_C\}$ in cycles/sec, where $f_A < f_{M_i} < f_C$. Each device has associated wait times $\mathcal{W} = \{w_A, w_{M_1}, \dots, w_{M_N}, w_C\}$ in seconds when these devices are already computing other tasks before the offloading tasks' arrival.

At time slot t , A performs local computation for patient acuity determination using the NTS acuity levels and streams vital signs to the ED. Task deadlines δ^t are assigned based on patient urgency levels according to the NTS acuity levels as $\delta_{U0} < \delta_{U1} < \delta_{U2} < \delta_{U3} < \delta_{U4} < \delta_{U5}$, assuming that critical patients (U0) require the shortest processing deadlines and least urgent cases (U5) allow longer completion times.

With available computational capacity of A , that is, $f_A^{a,t} < f_A$, AI tasks are processed locally at A or offloaded to M_i based on patient urgency $U^{P,t}$, network state G_{net}^t , task type τ^t , input and output data payloads as ρ_{in}^t , ρ_{out}^t respectively, deadline δ^t , battery capacity $b_A^{a,t}$, and available computation $f_A^{a,t}$. The metadata vector I^t contains anonymised patient/ambulance IDs, GPS coordinates, destination hospital, and timestamps.

The task vector is given by:

$$\mathbf{T}^t = \{U^{P,t}, G_{net}^t, \tau^t, \rho_{in}^t, \rho_{out}^t, \delta^t, f_A^{a,t}, b_A^{a,t}, I^t\} \quad (1)$$

which is transmitted to the nearest M_i via its access point. M_i has the real-time computational resource availability information of the ambulance to hospital pathway MECs $\{f_{M_{i+k}}, \dots, f_{M_N}\}$ (where, $1 \leq k \leq N - i$) and CS f_C . Then M_i determines optimal offloading decisions within deadline δ^t at the time slot t . If adequate resources are available, M_i requests A to send ρ_{in}^t . Otherwise, M_i sends a message to A about the resource unavailability. In case of resource

¹<https://www.de-nts.nl/>

availability message from M_i to A , ρ_{in}^t is sent from A to M_i . Then after successful computation, M_i returns result ρ_{out}^t to A directly or via M_{i+k} by rerouting. Otherwise, A processes locally or retries at subsequent time slots until the ambulance arrives at the receiving hospital.

B. Communication Model

At time slot t , the uplink transmission rate v_{A,M_i}^t between A and M_i and the associated latency $l_{A,M_i}^{comm,t}$ are given by:

$$v_{A,M_i}^t = B_{A,M_i}^t \cdot \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_A \cdot h_{A,M_i}^t \cdot d_{A,M_i}^{-\alpha}}{\sigma^2 + I} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$l_{A,M_i}^{comm,t} = \frac{\rho_{in}^t}{v_{A,M_i}^t} \quad (3)$$

where B^t is channel bandwidth (Hz), P_A is transmit power (Watts) from A , h_{A,M_i}^t is channel gain, d_{A,M_i} is distance, α is path loss exponent, σ^2 is noise power, and I is interference power between A and M_i .

Similarly, the downlink transmission rate $v_{M_i,A}^t$ and communication latency $l_{M_i,A}^{comm,t}$ are given by:

$$v_{M_i,A}^t = B_{M_i,A}^t \cdot \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_{M_i} \cdot h_{M_i,A}^t \cdot d_{M_i,A}^{-\alpha}}{\sigma^2 + I} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$l_{M_i,A}^{comm,t} = \frac{\rho_{out}^t}{v_{M_i,A}^t} \quad (5)$$

where the parameters follow the same definitions as equations 2 and 3 but for the reverse communication link.

Communication links between any M_i and C use high-speed fibre optic connections with negligible latency, which is assumed to be zero.

C. Computation Model

At time slot t , AI tasks execute either on A , M_i , or C . For task \mathbf{T}^t , let c^t (cycles/bit) denote CPU workload for processing input data ρ_{in}^t (bits) and $f_D^{a,t}$ represent available CPU capacity at node $D \in \{A, M_i, C\}$.

Processing latency at node D is given by:

$$l_D^{comp,t} = \frac{c^t \cdot \rho_{in}^t}{f_D^{a,t}} \quad (6)$$

where $f_D^{a,t} \leq f_D$ is dynamically updated based on background workload.

Total computation latency includes queue wait time w_D^t :

$$L_D^{comp,t} = w_D^t + l_D^{comp,t} \quad (7)$$

The communication latency between the in-ambulance sensors/devices and the edge computing device A is assumed to be zero. So the total system latency for task execution locally is only comprised of the computation latency, which is given by:

$$L_A^{tot,t} = L_A^{comp,t} \quad (8)$$

D. Total System Latency

The total system latency for offloaded tasks to M_i and C are given by:

$$L_{A,M_i}^{tot,t} = l_{A,M_i}^{comm,t} + L_{M_i}^{comp,t} + l_{M_i,A}^{comm,t}, \quad (9)$$

$$L_{A,C}^{tot,t} = l_{A,M_i}^{comm,t} + l_{M_i,C}^{comm,t} + L_C^{comp,t} + l_{C,M_i}^{comm,t} + l_{M_i,A}^{comm,t} \quad (10)$$

Where M_i - C links have negligible latency as they are assumed to be connected by fiber optic cables.

E. Energy Consumption Model

Local computation energy consumption E_A^t and offloading transmission energy $E_{A,D}^t$ are given by:

$$E_A^t = \kappa \cdot c^t \cdot \rho_{in}^t \cdot (f_A^{a,t})^2, \quad (11)$$

$$E_{A,D}^t = P_A \cdot l_{A,M_i}^{comm,t} \quad (12)$$

where κ is the switched capacitance coefficient.

F. Task Success Constraints

Task \mathbf{T}^t succeeds if the total latency meets the deadline:

$$L_{A,\mathcal{D} \setminus A}^{tot,t} \leq \delta^t \quad (13)$$

Failed tasks may be retried at the next time slot or executed locally if feasible.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We formulate the task offloading problem in PHEM as an MDP to capture the dynamic nature of ambulance environments, depending on patient acuity, network conditions, and resource availability. The MDP framework enables sequential decision-making under uncertainty, which is essential for real-time offloading decisions in time-critical PHEM scenarios.

Let $\mathcal{M} = \langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{R}, \gamma \rangle$ denote the MDP, where \mathcal{S} is the state space, \mathcal{A} is the action space, \mathcal{P} is the state transition probability, \mathcal{R} is the reward function, and $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ is the discount factor for future rewards.

A. State Space

The state $s^t \in \mathcal{S}$ at time slot t captures comprehensive system conditions relevant for offloading decisions:

$$s^t = \{ \mathbf{T}^t, \mathbf{G}_{net}^t, \mathbf{F}_{MEC}^t, \mathbf{W}^t \} \quad (14)$$

The state vector includes the \mathbf{T}^t from equation 1. Network conditions are captured by $\mathbf{G}_{net}^t = \{ R_{A,M_i}^t, h_{A,M_i}^t, d_{A,M_i} \}$ representing transmission rates, channel gains, and distances to M_i . The vector $\mathbf{F}_{MEC}^t = \{ f_{M_1}^{a,t}, \dots, f_{M_N}^{a,t}, f_C^{a,t} \}$ represents available computing capacities across M_i and C , while $\mathbf{W}^t = \{ w_{M_1}^t, \dots, w_{M_N}^t, w_C^t \}$ denotes wait times at each server.

B. Action Space

The action $a^t \in \mathcal{A}$ represents the offloading decision made by the PPO agent at time slot t . The discrete action space is:

$$\mathcal{A} = \{a_A, a_i, a_C\} \quad (15)$$

where a_A executes the task locally on A , a_i (for $i = 1, \dots, N$) offloads to M_i , and a_C offloads to C . The chosen action determines where task \mathbf{T}^t executes based on system state s^t to minimize latency while meeting deadline constraints (equation 13).

C. State Transition Probability

The state transition probability $\mathcal{P}(s^{t+1}|s^t, a^t)$ captures system evolution from time slot t to $t+1$ given action a^t , incorporating ambulance mobility affecting network conditions \mathbf{G}_{net}^{t+1} and M_i distances, where channel gains h_{A, M_i}^{t+1} evolve with movement, resource availability changes in computing capacities \mathbf{F}_{MEC}^{t+1} and queue states \mathbf{W}^{t+1} , battery depletion $b_A^{a, t+1}$ based on action a^t , and new emergency task arrivals with varying urgency levels $U^{P, t+1}$.

D. Reward Function

The reward function $\mathcal{R}(s^t, a^t)$ evaluates offloading decision quality by balancing latency minimization, deadline adherence, battery preservation, and NTS level:

$$\mathcal{R}(s^t, a^t) = \begin{cases} 1.0 - \frac{w_t}{\delta^t} & \text{if } L^{tot, t} \leq \delta^t \\ -1.0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The reward structure adapts to EM requirements by emphasizing deadline constraints over computational efficiency.

E. Objective Function

The objective is to find the optimal policy π^* that maximizes expected cumulative discounted reward:

$$\pi^* = \arg \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^t \mathcal{R}(s^t, a^t) | \pi \right] \quad (17)$$

subject to deadline, and computational and battery resource availabilities:

$$L_{chosen}^{tot, t} \leq \delta^t, \quad \forall t \quad (18)$$

$$f_D^{a, t} \geq f_{min}, \quad \forall t \quad \& \quad \forall D \in \{A, M_i, C\} \quad (19)$$

$$b_A^{a, t} \geq b_{min}, \quad \forall t \quad (20)$$

IV. PROXIMAL POLICY OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

PPO is an on-policy reinforcement learning algorithm that stabilizes policy gradient training by constraining policy updates through a clipped surrogate objective. Unlike traditional policy gradient methods that can suffer from catastrophic policy collapse, PPO limits the probability ratio between new and old policies within a controlled range $[1-\epsilon, 1+\epsilon]$, ensuring stable learning while maintaining computational simplicity compared to trust region methods [16]. This makes PPO

particularly suitable for dynamic environments like PHEM where stable, reliable decision-making is crucial.

We propose a PPO-based DRL framework for intelligent task offloading in PHEM. Our approach learns optimal offloading policies through on-policy optimization with stable policy updates, adapting to real-time EM scenarios, network conditions, and resource constraints.

A. PPO Agent Architecture

The PPO agent employs an actor-critic architecture with policy network $\pi(a|s; \theta)$ and value network $V(s; \phi)$. The policy network outputs action probabilities for the discrete action space \mathcal{A} (equation 15) while the value network estimates state values for advantage computation. Both networks share initial layers for efficient feature extraction from the normalised state vector s^t . The policy $\pi(a^t|s^t; \theta)$ represents the probability of taking action a^t in state s^t , while value $V(s^t; \phi)$ estimates the expected cumulative reward from state s^t .

B. PPO Training

PPO training incorporates the clipped surrogate objective, combining policy improvement with value function learning:

$$\mathcal{L}^{PPO}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\min(r_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{A}_t) \right] - c_1 \mathcal{L}^{VF}(\phi) + c_2 S[\pi_\theta](s_t) \quad (21)$$

Algorithm 1 PHEM-Aware PPO Training for Task Offloading

- 1: Initialize $\pi(a|s; \theta)$ and $V(s; \phi)$
 - 2: Set $\alpha = 0.0003$, $N_{batch} = 64$, $N_{steps} = 2048$
 - 3: **for** episode = 1 to $N_{episodes}$ **do**
 - 4: Initialize trajectory buffer $\mathcal{B} = \{\}$
 - 5: **for** step $t = 0$ to N_{steps} **do**
 - 6: Observe state $s^t = \{\mathbf{T}^t, \mathbf{G}_{net}^t, \mathbf{F}_{MEC}^t, \mathbf{W}^t\}$
 - 7: Sample action $a^t \sim \pi(\cdot|s^t; \theta)$
 - 8: Execute a^t , observe reward
 - 9: $r^t = \begin{cases} 1.0 - w_t/\delta^t & \text{if } L^{tot, t} \leq \delta^t \\ -1.0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$
 - 10: Store $(s^t, a^t, r^t, V(s^t), \log \pi(a^t|s^t))$ in \mathcal{B}
 - 11: **if** episode terminates **then**
 - 12: **break**
 - 13: **end if**
 - 14: **end for**
 - 15: Compute advantages $\hat{A}_t = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\gamma \lambda)^l \delta_{t+l}$ using GAE with $\lambda = 0.95$
 - 16: **for** epoch = 1 to K_{epochs} **do**
 - 17: Sample mini-batch from \mathcal{B}
 - 18: Compute PPO loss: $L^{PPO}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t [\min(r_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{A}_t)] - c_1 \mathcal{L}^{VF}(\phi) + c_2 S[\pi_\theta](s_t)$
 - 19: Update networks: $\theta \leftarrow \theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} L^{PPO}(\theta)$, $\phi \leftarrow \phi - \alpha \nabla_{\phi} L^{VF}(\phi)$
 - 20: **end for**
-

where $r_t(\theta) = \frac{\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{old}}(a_t|s_t)}$ is the probability ratio, \hat{A}_t is the advantage estimate, $\epsilon = 0.2$ is the clipping parameter, $\mathcal{L}^{VF}(\phi) = (V_\phi(s_t) - V_t^{target})^2$ is the value function loss, and $S[\pi_\theta](s_t)$ is the entropy bonus. Advantages are computed using generalized advantage estimation (GAE) with $\lambda = 0.95$:

$$\hat{A}_t = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\gamma\lambda)^l \delta_{t+l} \quad (22)$$

where $\delta_t = r_t + \gamma V(s_{t+1}) - V(s_t)$. PHEM-aware exploration reduces entropy for critical patients by modifying $c_2^t = c_{2,\min}$ if $U^{P,t} \in \{U0, U1\}$ and $c_{2,\text{base}}$ otherwise. The detailed PPO training algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS AND RESULTS

The proposed PPO-based offloading framework is evaluated on a synthetic PHEM dataset generated to mimic dynamic ambulance-edge-MEC-cloud operations under realistic variability. The dataset comprises 5,000 response episodes of 20 sequential offloading decisions each, for a total of 100,000 decision points. All tasks, ranging from vital-sign monitoring and HD video streaming to AI-based diagnostics, report generation, and EHR storage, have payload sizes ranging from 100 MB to 5 GB, ensuring substantial data-size diversity across all NTS levels. Network congestion, MEC server load and queue length, ambulance battery level, and uplink/downlink speeds evolve per step with controlled randomness. Battery drain per task and recharge per step are set to emphasize energy constraints, and MEC wait times incorporate both queue-length and stochastic delays. One ambulance edge device, one CS, and 10 MEC servers were set up, each MEC having a variable processing speed and downlink rate. Deadlines combined fixed NTS-level targets (20–120 seconds), but the distribution of the data was similar across all NTS levels.

The PPO model utilizes Stable-Baselines3’s default `MlpPolicy`, which ingests an 88-dimensional observation vector that includes network state, device status, MEC metrics, and workflow context, and outputs three discrete actions (local edge, MEC, or cloud). The policy and value networks each consist of two shared fully connected layers of 64 neurons, followed by separate heads (3 neurons for the actor, 1 for the critic)—training proceeds for 10^6 timesteps with parallel sampling. Key hyperparameters are listed in Table I.

A. Performance Results

Figure 2 compares task offloading success rates of four algorithms, PPO (blue), GA (green), PSO (yellow), and SA (red), across six NTS acuity levels. PPO consistently outperforms classical methods, especially under tight deadlines (U0 and U1), where it maintains success rates above 97% while others drop significantly. As deadlines relax (U2 to U5), all algorithms achieve high success rates, narrowing the performance gap. PPO also shows the least variability across levels, underscoring its reliability for time-sensitive PHEM applications.

TABLE I
SYSTEM PARAMETERS AND IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

Parameter	Value
Episodes	5 000
Steps per episode	20
Ambulances	1 edge device
MEC servers	10 nodes
Payload size	100 to 5000 MB
Network congestion	Mean 0.5, var 0.2
Battery drain/recharge	0.02 / 0.01 fraction per task/step
Deadline multiplier	Mean 5.0, var 1.5
Total timesteps	10^6
Policy architecture	MlpPolicy: shared layers
Actor head	3 neurons
Critic head	1 neuron
Learning rate	3×10^{-4} (Adam)
Discount factor	0.99
GAE	0.95
Clipping range	0.2
Steps per update	2 048
Epochs per update	4
Batch size	64

Figure 3 presents overall success averaged across all levels, with PPO leading at nearly 99%, followed by PSO, SA, and GA. This aggregate view highlights PPO’s superior consistency and efficacy in dynamic edge-MEC-cloud task offloading.

Fig. 2. Task offloading success rates for each optimization algorithm across Netherlands Triage Standard acuity levels (U0: Most Critical, Shortest Deadline; U5: Least Critical, Longest Deadline).

Figure 3 summarizes the overall deadline adherence of each algorithm averaged across all NTS levels. PPO again leads with nearly 99% success rate, followed by PSO, SA, and GA in descending order. This aggregated view reinforces PPO’s robustness and reliability in maximizing timely task completions under varied urgency conditions.

VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Experimental evaluation on a large synthetic PHEM dataset confirms that the PPO-based offloading framework achieves the highest and most consistent task success rates across all NTS acuity levels, with an overall success rate approaching 99% (Fig. 3). PPO’s policy effectively balances latency and

Fig. 3. Overall task offloading success rate averaged across all NTS acuity levels for each optimization algorithm.

computational load by dynamically selecting between ambulance edge, MEC, and cloud resources in response to task urgency, network congestion, and battery state. Traditional optimizers (GA, PSO, SA) fall behind under tight deadlines (U0 and U1), exhibiting greater variability and lower success rate, yet converge toward high performance as deadlines relax (U2 to U5), as shown in Fig. 2.

The persistent performance gap under critical conditions underscores PPO’s ability to integrate heterogeneous state information, NTS acuity levels, connectivity, and resource availability through its MDP formulation and GAE-enhanced policy updates. Stability analysis reveals PPO’s minimal variance across scenarios, an essential property for reliable PHEM support.

These experiments used homogeneous distributions for payload sizes, network bandwidth, and computational workloads across all acuity levels, differing only in deadline constraints. Introducing realistic, acuity-dependent variations, such as higher-resolution imaging for critical cases, heterogeneous network coverage between urban and rural environments, and variable resource contention, could reveal divergent algorithm behaviors and more nuanced performance trends. Our future work will focus on generating datasets informed by real patient records and operational telemetry to capture acuity-specific task profiles. We will also explore multi-agent reinforcement learning for coordinated offloading in mass-casualty scenarios and integrate actual geolocation and network datasets (e.g., OpenCellID, national hospital registries) to refine policy adaptation under authentic operational constraints. These efforts will further optimize the PPO framework for robust, low-latency AI support in diverse PHEM contexts.

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